

Disaster Preparedness and Response Education System for Schools and Colleges

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Abstract:- Natural disasters like earthquake, floods, cyclones and fires act as great threats to human life and infrastructure. In such situations, one of the major challenges is lack of awareness and improper decision-making by the individuals. Traditional disaster education methods are theoretical, hence fail to deal with real life emergency situations. Hence an interactive disaster management system is presented to engage in realistic disaster scenarios. The project is demonstrated using full stack architecture. The proposed system enhances disaster preparedness through realistic learning and provides engaging solution for disaster awareness training.

Keywords:- Disaster Management, Emergency Preparedness, Simulation-Based Learning, Web Application, Disaster Response Training, Preparedness Index, Gamification.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lack of awareness and preparedness is one of the major reasons for casualty during disasters. People panic and take incorrect actions due to insufficient knowledge about

safety measures. Therefore, educating the individuals on disaster management proves to be very important. Traditional methods include lectures, awareness campaigns and guidelines. These are mostly theoretical and do not prepare individuals for real-life situations. They lack interaction and the situation of urgency and pressure under actual emergencies. Therefore, there is a need for more practical learning approaches that helps users to understand disaster scenarios.

To bridge this gap, this paper presents an interactive disaster management training system that uses simulation-based learning. It helps users by providing various modules, drill exercises and a personalized performance dashboard. By combining these concepts, the system aims to improve disaster awareness preparedness during emergencies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the years, Disaster management and preparedness have been studied to reduce risks and improve the

response systems. Organizations like the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (2023) highlight the importance of public awareness in reducing disaster impact.

In recent years, simulation-based learning is in demand for disaster education. Training programs that are developed by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (2022) show hands-on experience in simulated environments.

Web-based disaster management platforms are also popular due to high accessibility and scalability. One such example is Google Crisis Response platform. It provides users real-time alerts and safety guidance. These platforms portray the improvements after integrating technology with disaster management system.

In addition to this, studies in Lee et al., 2020 indicate that through gamification, user engagement and learning outcomes are increased. By including activities like feedback and rewards, users feel motivated enough to actively participate in training systems.

2.1 Research Gap

Though the current platforms help by providing disaster awareness and basic training, they do lack interactive simulation and performance evaluation. In addition to that, very few integrate user training and monitoring in a single platform. This showcases the need for systems that are capable of combining simulation learning and analytics.

3. THE METHODOLOGY

The project has focused on improving disaster management using simulation-based learning. Structured learning, drills and evaluation are all provided on one single platform.

It is a full stack application built with MERN Stack.

The technologies present in this project are

- Frontend: React
- Backend: Node.js
- Data Storage: MongoDB

Fig 1. System Flow Diagram

3.1 Learning Module Design

This component has multiple disaster categories like earthquake, flood, cyclone and fire. Each category is a detailed module. Every module has certain introduction, safety instructions and precautions. These help users to get basic knowledge before trying drills.

3.2 Drill-Based Simulation

Drill-based simulation is the core function of this project. Users are presented with disaster scenarios. They should choose right actions based on each situation.

- Each drill is based on real-life scenarios.
- The drills are presented as multiple choice.
- The system will evaluate the response by user.
- Performance feedback will be given to the user.

Fig 2. Process flow of disaster training system

3.3 Data Management

MongoDB is the primary source for data handling and data storage. All the user data like drill scores, modules, learning progress are stored in the database. The backend APIs will handle all the data update and retrievals. This whole process ensures user progress is always maintained in sessions.

3.4 Performance Evaluation

This component evaluated the user performance using a metric called Preparedness Index. This index helps to give quantitative measure on how well user has understood disaster situations.

The preparedness index is calculated based on these factors:

- Module completion – learning progress
- Drill scores - performance accuracy
- Number of drills attempted - consistency

Through these evaluations, users get to identify their areas of strengths, weakness and improvements.

3.5 Admin Dashboard

This component is accessible only for instructors and administrators to manage modules and monitor student performance.

Key functionalities of admin dashboard are:

- Module Management: Admins can easily add, edit, delete and reorder learning modules.
- Performance Monitoring: Dashboard displays student scores module completion rate and drill scores.
- Analytics and Visualization: Bar charts and pie charts are used to analyze student performances, average scores and enrollment distribution.
- Leaderboard and Insights: Generate insights that help to identify top performing students and their improvement areas.

3.6 Advantage of disaster preparedness

This system has many advantages over traditional methods. They are as follows:

- Users are provided with interactive learning through simulation drills.
- Understand real life emergency effectively.
- Track progress of users using evaluation metrics.

3. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

It has a three-tier architecture. It has three layers - frontend, backend and database. This is to maintain the scalability and data handling throughout the whole process.

4.1 Frontend Layer

React is the major frontend component used. It helps with interface rendering and user interaction. Components like modules, drill, simulations, dashboards are present here. React routing helps to navigate to different sections of the application.

Fig 3. Architectural Design

4.2 Backend Layer

Node.js is used to setup the backend. API endpoints are used for data handling. Backend deals with user authentication and session handling. Through this, all admin actions are done securely too. It acts as a bridge between database and frontend.

In summary, backend helps to keep the application secure. It processes every user data and operations.

4.3 Database Layer

MongoDB is used for data storage and management. It stores all the content like categories, performances and

scores. It tracks and updates all the user data. MongoDB ensures flexible schema designs.

5. CONCLUSION

To conclude, this platform provides better preparedness among users. Traditional systems do provide help, but with only passive learning. Whereas, DisasterPrep involves realistic scenes that helps users understand to make decision.

There are unique features like preparedness index and personalized dashboards. Student dashboard helps the users track their progress and know their areas of improvement.

Admin dashboards can manage and view all the student performances.

This is also a responsive platform accessible to wide range of users. It combines education, simulation and analytics in a single platform. Therefore, a suitable solution for disaster preparedness.

For future enhancements, project can be advanced for mobile apps, receive real time alerts through SMS/emails. AI can be used to personalize UX and improve training methods.

6. REFERENCES

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